

THE NECESSITY AND IMPORTANCE OF DEVELOPING ECOLOGICAL CULTURE IN FUTURE ENGINEERS

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***Abstract.** The article presents the main functions and tasks of engineering activities, the content of the function of technical forecasting and analysis. Based on the analysis, the main directions of the engineering profession are identified and the current lack of attention to such functions as technical-aesthetic and engineering ecology is justified. The definition of the concepts of engineering ecology and ecological culture is clarified, and the inextricable link between professional culture, labor culture, engineering culture and ecological culture is revealed. Methods for developing ecological culture are described.*

***Keywords:** engineer, function, task, profession, ecological culture, technical-aesthetic, ecology, method.*

INTRODUCTION

The digitalization of modern industrial production, energy, agriculture and other sectors of the economy, the use of cloud technologies, artificial intelligence, robots, the creation of projects such as smart cities or smart agriculture require the expansion and improvement of modern requirements for future engineers. The structure and functions of engineering activities have been continuously developing in accordance with the spirit of the times since the emergence of engineering work as a separate profession [1]. Engineering activities are mainly carried out in the technosphere environment, but also reflect the interaction between the technosphere and the biosphere.

RESEARCH METHODS

The study used analytical, predictive, comparative and statistical analysis methods, as well as empirical methods: questionnaires, observation, test questions, interviews, open-ended ideas, and analysis of experimental test results.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Modern engineers perform the following tasks in the development of modern techniques and technologies and production (see figure) [2,3]:

- create and develop modern technologies (digital, cloud technologies, mobile communications and modern types of computers, robots, artificial intelligence, etc.)
- design and construct infrastructure (buildings and structures, smart cities, roads, airports, bridges, etc.);
- improve production processes (develop new methods of production aimed at improving product quality, increasing production efficiency and reducing costs);
- create new products and services;
- develop environmentally friendly technologies.

The main tasks of modern engineers

Based on the above tasks, engineering activities can be divided into internal and external functions. External functions include social factors, namely humanistic, socio-economic, managerial, educational, and the development of the technical base of society. Internal functions include technical factors, namely functions aimed at the development of production, such as technical forecasting and analysis, technological support, research developments, projects, operation and repair of equipment, as well as the technical forecasting and analysis function of the engineer. Since the fields of engineering are diverse and multifaceted, the system design function also plays an important role [4,5].

The function of technical forecasting and analysis of an engineer is explained by the adjustment of the relationship between production needs and technical resistance. In this case, the technical policy and main parameters of engineering tasks are determined on the basis of identifying the prospects and trends of technical development. Chief engineers, leading specialists of research and design and construction institutes, laboratories are involved in the implementation of these tasks. Based on the analysis, the future technical system and technology are predicted, ideas are created.

The following functions are performed in engineering activities: research, design, technological, production adjustment, engineer of equipment operation and repair, system design.

From the analysis of the above engineering functions, the following areas of the engineering profession arise: technical forecasting and analysis engineer; research engineer; design engineer; design engineer; engineer technologist; production engineer; engineer for operation and repair of technical systems; system design engineer[6,7] In our opinion, this proposed classification does not fully cover the functions of modern engineering activity. Because this classification does not include such functions as technical-aesthetic and engineering ecology.

Technical-aesthetic compatibility also plays an important role in ergonomics. It is known that in engineering ergonomics there are mainly 5 types of requirements and compatibility (information, energy, biophysical, spatial-anthropometric and technical-aesthetic), one of which is technical-aesthetic compatibility. Technical-aesthetic compatibility includes the design, color,

dimensions of the equipment, etc. Namely, nowadays, when purchasing any equipment, an organization or enterprise or an individual pays great attention to its design and color. This, in turn, has a great impact on the occupational safety, labor productivity and mood of the person (worker) using this equipment.

Engineering ecology (environmental engineering) is a set of scientific and engineering principles aimed at improving the natural environment by ensuring the purity of water, air, and soil for the survival of humans and other organisms and for the remediation of polluted areas [8].

In order to ensure a high level of ecological safety of human economic activities and reduce anthropogenic impact on the environment, the tasks of environmental engineers include the design, development, use and improvement of techniques and technologies aimed at environmental protection, the organization of environmental protection work in organizations and enterprises, certification of projects, technologies, manufactured products, etc. [9]. The tasks of engineering ecology include maintaining public health, waterborne diseases, maintaining the sanitary and hygienic condition of urban and rural areas, i.e. wastewater treatment, air pollution control, waste recycling, industrial sanitation, environmental sustainability of public health, research into the impact of construction projects on the environment, and knowledge of engineering laws of environmental protection.

Environmental engineers study the impact of technological progress on the environment, that is, they evaluate harmful technical waste and develop recommendations for its disposal. Also, global and local environmental problems, including acid rain, global warming, ozone layer depletion, water, air and soil pollution, and the protection of wildlife and plants, are among the main tasks assigned to environmental engineers.

Since the time when humanity realized that its health and well-being depended on the environment, they began to implement measures to improve the quality of the living environment. The ancient Harappan civilization used collectors in some cities. In Rome, in order to prevent drought and provide the city with clean air and clean water, an aqueduct (Latin aqua - water and dico - to carry), aqueduct-bridge - a bridge-like, trestle-shaped water-conducting structure consisting of a branch or pipe that is passed over a ravine, gorge, river, road. Depending on the length and depth of the passage, it is built of wood, reinforced concrete, stone, concrete and metal). Ecological engineering as a separate discipline arose in the middle of the 20th century due to water and air pollution and environmental degradation. However, its history can also be linked to the development of a sewage system project by Joseph Bazeldjet in London in the 9th century.

The above analytical data provides general information about the engineer-ecologist, but this dissertation sets the task of developing the ecological culture of engineers in other fields (industry, agriculture, digital technologies, energy, chemical technology, food technology, etc.). Therefore, it is necessary to improve the methodology for developing the ecological culture of engineers in the process of training future engineers in technical universities, to substantiate its essence and content, necessity and significance. Therefore, in solving research tasks, it is necessary to determine and analyze the connection between the professional culture of an engineer, labor culture, engineering culture and ecological culture.

Therefore, today, higher technical educational institutions of Uzbekistan are tasked with training competitive engineers who fully meet international standards. A higher educational institution must be able to form a professional culture in future engineers, and future engineers must be able to consciously understand the essence, necessity and difference of professional, labor and engineering cultures and have the ability to continuously develop them throughout their

professional activities. However, it can be considered that the current process of training engineers in higher education does not have the full conditions for the formation of a professional and engineering culture that fully meets the requirements of the time. Because, although the resulting activity of education is aimed at forming professional competence in future engineers, since education is organized on the basis of a competency approach, they do not have the opportunity to fully acquire the skills to comprehensively solve problems in life and production activities. An engineer trained on the basis of a competency approach can adapt only if changes in the labor market are not significant. However, if the demand for this specialty decreases sharply due to the needs of society or the attitude towards work changes, an engineer trained on the basis of a competency approach will not be able to adapt to new working conditions. Therefore, it is necessary to develop the educational process based on a competency approach together with culture (professional, labor, engineering cultures). This will lead to the development of the individual both professionally and culturally.

Ecological culture is a conscious approach to environmental protection, living in harmony with nature and saving resources. This should be reflected not only in personal life, but also in professional activities. The ecological culture of engineers is understood as the development of measures to minimize the biophysical factors arising in the design and use of new modern equipment and technologies, to reduce their impact on the environment.

According to the Glossary of Environmental Education in line with the Sustainable Development Goals until 2030, "ecological culture is a culture of actions and behavior in socio-natural ecological systems aimed at preserving the quality of the natural environment. Achieving the level of modern requirements of ecological culture is carried out on the basis of environmental education aimed at developing environmental literacy, ecological thinking, and practical ecological experiences in the natural environment.

CONCLUSION

The development of ecological culture is carried out in close connection with the following:

- paying great attention to environmental education in education and upbringing;
- implementing innovative technologies; developing environmentally friendly solutions in the field of improving techniques and technologies;
- compliance with environmental protection standards;
- using international cooperation and the experience of developed countries.

The development of the ecological culture of future engineers in higher technical educational institutions should be carried out on the basis of interdisciplinary integration of not only the teaching of ecology, but also of specialized disciplines. In particular, it is advisable to carry out such areas as the design and use of renewable energy sources (solar panels, wind turbines and other environmentally friendly energy sources), the development of "smart cities", "smart agriculture" and other similar smart projects, water, air, soil protection, waste management (recycling, storage, etc.).

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